

Networks and textual production during the Middle Ages (12th–15th centuries)

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In this article we would like to demonstrate how social network analysis can lead us to establish historical hypotheses regarding the production of books in the Middle Ages.

To this end, we have identified 125 digitalized manuscripts containing scientific texts preserved in the Bibliothèque nationale de France. We will justify the acquisition and curation of this data. Insofar as the experiment should be continued on a larger scale. To compile a usable dataset from these digitalized manuscripts, we carried out image segmentation in order to identify lines of text and other codicological elements using *dbSegment* (Ares Oliveira, 2019). The data, resulting from the processing of these lines of text allowed us to be able to reconstruct the layout of the text on the pages.

Our approach proposes to unlink the manuscripts in order to examine not the books but the texts' copies contained in these *codices*, which we call “witnesses”. This comparison is based on metrics resulting from quantitative codicology. To our knowledge, there has never been such a study compiling and exploiting such detailed and precise data, making it possible to account for the layout of so many manuscripts.

Based on the data collected, we have built a graph network of these factures (*i.e.* text making). This graph constitutes a new source of information that has been analyzed to study the production of scientific texts in the Middle Ages. This is an original approach and network analysis in humanities academic field have traditionally focused on the study of social groups, and not object production as we have done here.

In this graph of text factures, each node is a witness and each of these witnesses are described by a set of measures allowing us to understand its layout. The edges of the graph are valuated according to the number of codicological measures for which the two witnesses share proximities. The valuation of the edges therefore corresponds to the degree of similarity between the witnesses. The construction of this network and the use of social network analysis tools enable us to obtain a classification that is better suited for the accounting of contacts, which are likely to reflect the formatting habits of witnesses, than those we could have obtained using more “traditional” clustering methods.

To establish our classification, we compare two clustering approaches: the hierarchical algorithm of the Louvain method (Blondel and *al.*, 2008), and the stochastic blockmodels (Holland, 1983). The use of these algorithms enabled us to isolate seven clusters. This corpus-driven classification, which emanates from the structure of the data, makes it possible to reflect on what we think we know about the layout of scientific texts by observing isolated individuals.

In order to interpret these clusters, more traditional quantitative analysis techniques are used. In particular, we used a type of multivariate statistical analysis: multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) (Escofier and Pagès, 2016). MCA enabled to understand which codicological measures were most important in discriminating classifications. On the basis of these explorations, we were able to isolate what characterizes text facture classes resulting from the use of clustering algorithms mentioned above.

Like the members of the QUANTICOD group (QUANTICOD, 1985), we consider the medieval book as a “machine with a complex operation” (Bozzolo, 1990). For us, the theme of the text is one of these many constraints. It may be less determining than the wealth of the patron, but it is a relevant and important cultural constraint, which plays a part in the production of the book object, right down to its physical appearance. Therefore, we wanted to observe the impact of this constraint and understand the results. To this end, we projected onto the network data, that had not been used to calculate it, *i.e.* the data relating to the themes of the witnesses. This data comes from the informations available in the catalog of the Bibliothèque nationale de France and in the online database of scientific manuscripts *Jodanus*, which we have requalified. We hypothesized an impact on the theme of the text on its layout. This hypothesis was confirmed, since we were able to see that the classes we had obtained brought together a number of thematics in a coherent way for medieval society. Therefore, we have observed and demonstrated the existence of a non-negligible impact of a text's thematic, within the sciences, in the way the page is laid out.

To consolidate our results, we compared them with another method that can produce a corpus-driven classification: self-organizing maps (Kohonen, 1995). The result was a very similar classification, confirming our interpretation.

The approach developed in this paper is innovative in that it mobilizes techniques which, to our humble knowledge, had not previously been used in quantitative codicology. From our perspective, this demonstrates the value of using network analysis in historical field, beyond the study of social groups. The network can also be a means of carrying out analyses and classifications based on resemblance rather than dissimilarity. Provided we distance ourselves from any interpretation that would subject our data to social mechanisms, the network can be a means of taking a fresh look at historical data.

Our study confirms the interest of research projects using artificial intelligence to acquire data on vast *corpora*. Indeed, artificial intelligence it possible to acquire codicological data on manuscripts that are not necessarily listed in the catalogs of conservation institutions, and to do so on large volumes of manuscripts.

References

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